

ASSESSING THE BARRIERS TO THE UPTAKE OF SUSTAINABLE ENGINEERED EARTHEN MASONRY SYSTEMS BY REAL ESTATE DEVELOPERS IN THE KENYAN CONSTRUCTION CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

There is a widespread believe that policy instruments can help scale the uptake of non-conventional building materials. Kenya's 2017 "Big Four Agenda" for food security, affordable health, manufacturing, and affordable housing provided an opportunity for proponents of non-conventional building materials to scale their uptake. The high-level Presidential pointed out that alternatives were necessary because conventional materials had failed to deliver the desired outcomes with respect to providing affordable housing at scale. The discussion in this paper examines the impact of this Presidential endorsement from the perspective of real estate developers. The study adopts a desk review and open-ended surveys. We focus specifically on engineered earthen masonry. It has emerged that despite the endorsement, alternative building materials are yet to claim a sizeable share of the market. Key barriers include insufficient structural performance data and regulations. Proponents of non-conventional building materials still need to generate empirical data that can underpin the development of standards, codes, performance, cost data and structure the supply chain that directly address existing concerns.

Key words: Market uptake, Social Acceptance, Engineered earthen masonry; Affordable Housing

INTRODUCTION

This paper builds on a series of NSF funded projects directed at advancing the structural use of engineered earthen masonry systems in low-income housing. The primary author has explored various strategies that can be used to optimize the physical and mechanical performance of these non-conventional materials in structures that can resist hygrothermal loads (Obonyo, 2011) as well as resisting lateral loads in high wind regions (Donkor & Obonyo, 2015).

More than 3 billion people will lack access to adequate housing by 2030. With the current exponential growth in population and sustained urban migration trends more than 60% of the projected 8.55 billion people will be living in urban areas by 2030 (United, 2018). The results is an unmet demand of 96,000 low-cost houses per day (UNHABITAT, 2019). The urbanization rate is alarming in sub-Saharan Africa. It is anticipated that 65.6% of the population will be living in urban areas by 2050. Such trends will leave a disproportionately large number of people inadequately housed and more than 1 million others homeless (Kenya, 2019). The urbanization process is not accompanied by substantial economic progress as initially assumed (United, 2018). Currently, more than 189 million urban dwellers in sub-Saharan Africa reside in

slums. In Kenya, only 2% of the total housing stock is accessible to the low-income population. The country experiences an annual deficit of 200,000 units of affordable housing (Habitat for Humanity, 2022), with 60% living in slums or slum-like conditions (Babijes, 2016). The current housing supply patterns are also unsustainable as far as the use of limited resources and greenhouse gas emissions is concerned. 40% of the global raw materials and 38% of the global emissions are from the built environment, 10% of the emissions can be attributed to building materials. Building materials account for 60 - 65% of the total construction costs hence a significant determinant of housing affordability. Conventional building materials utilize significant amounts of energy from fossil fuels and non-renewable raw material sources rendering them unsustainable. Their global transportation due to unlocalized production increases not only their embodied carbon but also the final costs incurred by developers and building owners (Melià et al., 2014). The use of non-conventional building materials such as the engineered earthen masonry bricks have gained popularity due to their sustainability and affordability, they could increase the supply of adequate affordable and sustainable housing. Because the input material is locally sourced, they offer a cost-effective solution. This opportunity provides a lever to drive the change towards a scaled uptake of these earthen materials (Melià et al., 2014).

Notwithstanding these benefits, earthen masonry bricks are mostly used in informal rural housing (Giulia Celentano & Habert, 2021). Efforts to encourage their use in the formal housing systems started over four decades ago. Initiatives that successfully deployed earthen masonry systems in formal housing include projects implemented by the Housing and Building Research Institute (HABRI), a research and development enterprise that was run by the University of Nairobi for several years (Schreckenbach, 1992). There have also been other more recent examples linked to targeted marketing of technology for producing compressed earth bricks. We have observed that efforts to scale such initiative beyond pilot and case study projects are often met with some resistance. These include concerns about the structural integrity of such materials discussed during an NSF-funded US-Tanzania workshop that was chaired by the first author. We have continued with efforts directed at addressing these concerns through optimizing earthen masonry to resist hygrothermal loads in the hot and humid East African context. We have also demonstrated that fiber-reinforced masonry can be used in regions where building systems can be exposed to high wind loads (Cuéllar-Azcárate, 2016; Obonyo, 2011).

Various research groups have identified strategies that can be used to optimize such materials against all the common structural performance, affordability and environmental sustainability metrics. Similar to the outcomes in other closely related research, the authors have observed that some of the barriers are connected to social acceptance, or in this case, the lack thereof (Ghazvinian & Leung, 2021). Conventional materials such as fired bricks and concrete-based masonry systems continue to dominate the market despite their known high embodied carbon and costs leading to higher costs of housing. (Ben-Alon et al., 2019; Melià et al., 2014).

On the supply side of the market, proponents of earthen masonry systems have for several decades argued the prevailing regulatory and policy framework favored the use of conventional building materials. In 2017 these concerns were addressed through affordable housing being identified as one of the pillars for what was dubbed “The Big Four Agenda” The Agenda specifically stated that conventional materials and technologies were not going to deliver the required solution. It advocated for the use of low-cost construction technologies and materials from the onset and promoting locally produced building materials. This sparked an interest in non-conventional building materials. An Affordable Housing Framework was created to propel and provide a guideline towards the delivery of 500,000 affordable housing units to the middle to low-income households in Kenya between 2018 and 2022 to reduce the low-income housing deficit which is projected to rise to 350,000 units per year if not well addressed. Five years later, low carbon building materials such as earthen masonry are yet to claim a sizeable share of the Kenyan construction market (Mwende, 2017). The construction of the targeted housing units by the government is still being undertaken using the conventional materials. This limits the possibility of mainstreaming the non-

conventional materials in the industry and lowering the price of housing to reach the level of affordability that is suitable for the low-income households. Concrete blocks account for 14% of the total material costs in residential buildings. This significantly inflates the material costs to more than 60% (Gardner et al., 2019).

The research discussed in this paper adopts a “looking back, looking forward” approach to probe these issues further. The specific goals of the study include: 1) identifying the impact of Kenya’s “Big Four Agenda” on the uptake of alternative low-carbon materials in the formal construction sector 2) exploring the barriers to the uptake of earthen masonry through a social acceptance lens, and 3) assessing the critical success factors for the uptake of engineered earthen masonry by real estate developers in Kenya. In the subsequent section, the authors have outlined the research methodology that was adopted for the research. This is followed by an overview of the key findings. The paper ends with a discussion of the implications of these findings.

METHODOLOGY

The authors adopted a mixed method of state-of-the-art desk review of related literature and a preliminary open-ended structured survey. An in-depth review of literature to identify the trends and gap in the uptake of engineered earthen masonry as an alternative low carbon material in formal real estate development projects was conducted. The authors also interacted with 6 subject matter experts through inviting them to respond to questions that focused on understanding their views on the critical factors that drive the use of engineering earthen masonry among real estate developers in the Kenyan context. The Qualtrics based survey consisted of a series of thirteen open ended questions. The research discussed in this paper focused on examining the responses to seven open questions that have been outlined below:

1. What drives your firm’s preferences when choosing materials for execution of your projects?
2. What drives your choice for these alternative walling systems?
3. How has the move towards affordable building materials influenced your interest in engineered earthen masonry system?
4. To what extent has your firm adopted the use of engineered earthen masonry as an alternative material to promote affordability of your projects?
5. What hinders the large-scale application of these earthen masonry materials in your development projects?
6. What factors can influence an increased uptake of the engineered earthen masonry materials in your large-scale development projects?
7. What can be done to achieve mass adoption of the engineered earthen masonry systems by the real estate developers in the Kenyan construction sector?

The Findings from both the literature and subject matter experts’ responses were grouped according to emerging themes – determinants of materials choices, barriers, and adoption drivers to the use of low carbon materials. These thematic areas were analyzed against the data that was acquired through the review of the state of the art in the deployment of engineered earthen masonry system. Figure 1 outlines the research flow adopted by the authors.

Figure 1: Research flow adopted by authors

KEY FINDINGS FROM LITERATURE

The building process consists of multiple stakeholders with diverse interests in the project. To achieve sustainability from individual project level to the large scale built environment level, a holistic systems approach must be embraced. The main barriers limiting mainstreaming of sustainable low carbon solutions have been associated with economic, technical, behavioral and perceptual bottlenecks within the policies and stakeholders’ institutions (Giesekam et al., 2014; Morel et al., 2021). Table 1 shows a summary of the major barriers that limit the uptake of low carbon materials by clients.

Table 1: Barriers to uptake of low carbon materials (Giesekam et al., 2014):(Gounder et al., 2021; Morel et al., 2021)

Barriers	Factors
Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High investment in conventional materials (training and research) • Increased materials lead times resulting from supply chain bottlenecks • Stiff competition from large scale conventional material producers • Lack of economies of scale in purchasing these low carbon materials • Instability in the supply chain • Additional design and construction costs due to increased detailing and additional technology • Lack of a strong developer-supplier relationship to sustain use
Technical and Regulatory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of widely acknowledged codes and standards that guide the use of the materials • Insufficient data on structural performance of materials • Lack of sufficient skilled labor and technology to accurately install these systems in formal construction • Lack of regulatory and policy backing and support for adoption of materials in formal construction

Barriers	Factors
Informational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of sufficient knowledge on the alternative material by developers • Lack of surety on policy provisions for material use • Insufficient knowledge on production standards • Insufficient awareness creation by material suppliers
Perceptual or sociological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural perceptions on the materials (social class indicator etc) • Clients and home buyer's preference for conventional materials • Existence of previous negative experience in the use of material

The authors assess the barriers that appear to have the most significant influence on Kenya's real estate developers in the subsequent subsections.

Dominance of conventional building materials in the formal construction sector

We can mitigate the high carbon emissions from the built environment through eliminating over reliance on the high embodied carbon materials (UNEP, 2021). This can be substituted with low carbon materials. These materials are sustainable and provide an affordable option for formalization of informal low cost housing (Gekonge, 2021). Their local production makes them low cost with ability to promote housing resilience and drive affordability in low-income housing. Affordable housing supply deficit has been a major setback to social and economic equality. The rapidly urbanizing urban environments increase the existing gap between demand and supply in affordable housing. Majority of the urban population have been thrown into poor housing conditions. In the case of Kenya, more than 50% of the urban population in the capital are not adequately housed (Giulia Celentano & Habert, 2021). Overreliance on conventional building materials in Kenya's construction industry, which reflects the global scenario, has made housing units unaffordable. Their high costs increase the overall construction costs and the final selling price of houses. In Nairobi, housing prices have increased by 4.21 fold over the last 10 years (Hass consult, 2021). 98% of these units cater for the middle- and high-income urban residents. The UN SDG indicators defines an affordable housing as one that does not cost more than 30% of the total income of a household (UNHABITAT, 2019). For a family that survives on an income below 4 dollars a day, this translates to a total cost of not more than \$ 16,000 (Van Noppen, 2012).

A major aspect that has been at the core of increasing affordability of low-income housing is the use of alternative building materials and technologies. The main alternative building material that has been the center-stage of low-cost construction in Kenya are the interlocking bricks. They are made from locally available soil and very little cement making them affordable. The downside of these bricks from the building owner's perspective has been their structural strength. The end result has been the application of these bricks majorly in informal residential construction (Van Noppen, 2012). Engineered earthen masonry systems adopt the above principle of locally available raw materials and low carbon production process, except with additional engineering of the properties to improve their structural performance under different loading.

Concerns over the structural performance of engineered earthen masonry

Earthen masonry bricks have undergone evolution in terms of their overall performance and production. The local availability of the raw materials reduces the overall embodied carbon. The process of their production also uses little to no energy resources making the carbon content much lower. Production of these systems in small scale at community level and in production facility increases their economic importance over and above the benefit of providing affordable housing units. Despite their low carbon content due to locally sources raw materials used in their production and their low costs, the downside of earthen bricks has been their performance.

They have been widely associated with low structural strength and stability which are perceived to likely result to failure of the system when carrying loads (Donkor & Obonyo, 2015). However, in majority of the cases, the stability and durability of these elements have been shown to result to more failures compared to the structural strength (Beckett et al., 2020; Gaitan, 2021; Ige & Danso, 2021; Obonyo, 2011). In other settings, earthen masonry systems have been investigated for their higher porosity compared to the concrete masonry counterparts, thereby limiting their adoption in areas that are prone to flooding (Bruno et al., 2017).

Over the years, research has continued to demonstrate that the shortcomings of earthen masonry can be mitigated through a series of engineering modifications to enhance their performance. The resulting improvements when exposed to different structural and environmental loadings signify their capability for large scale developments in the formal construction market. Some of the properties of earthen masonry systems that have been highly considered in their analysis as potential mainstream building materials include the strength enhancement (tensile and compressive), improved durability, stability, stiffness, thermal and moisture performance, and porosity. These improvements have been based on addition of complementary non-conventional locally sourced materials, binders and enhancers such as plantain fibers from agricultural wastes (Danso et al., 2015; Ige & Danso, 2021). Due to their high thermal mass, these materials provide sufficient heat to minimize the need for artificial heating in tropical climates during the cold weather.

Government-driven initiatives seeking to scale uptake of alternative building solutions

An implementation framework is required to guide a structured shift towards mainstreaming alternative low carbon materials and technologies in the formal construction sector. This needs backing from standards, codes, policies, and the government. The “big four agenda” incorporated a framework to guide realization of the affordable housing pillar. The framework leverages on the use of standardized and locally available alternative materials and technologies. An approach that incorporates the input of all stakeholders including material suppliers can help transform the informal local material production into a formalized supply chain. The transformation is dependent on stakeholders’ feedback for quality and performance improvement during production. Shift in the demand of the locally produced construction materials as a result of Kenya’s Big Four Affordable Housing Agenda has potential to influence demand by private developers and households over time (Gardner et al., 2019; Housing, 2018).

Challenges within the alternative earthen masonry supply chain

The availability of alternative and sustainable low-cost building materials is a direct product of demand and production that work towards meeting this demand. It requires a joint input from both the owners that intend to carry out the construction and the producers or suppliers of the material (G Celentano et al., 2020; Giulia Celentano & Habert, 2021). The uptake of the novel solutions in alternative building materials require in depth understanding of the capabilities of these materials by these two primary parties. The awareness of the performance and related concerns can be expounded to eliminate potential barriers and bottlenecks in the supply chain associated with lack of knowledge and biases towards the materials. (Giulia Celentano & Habert, 2021; Diarte et al., 2020; Ghazvinian & Leung, 2021). Alternative materials can only remain affordable provided the increase in demand is simultaneously countered with a corresponding supply to eliminate the need for outsourcing (Gardner et al., 2019). Localization of material production and consumption provides a low-cost and sustainable option for the earthen masonry (Cuéllar-Azcárate, 2016). To broaden the use of these low carbon masonry, a holistic supply chain which incorporates the producers, marketing, the construction professionals and the end users throughout the entire planning and construction process is essential (Giesekam et al., 2016).

Lack of a common driving factor in material choice among construction developers in Kenya

In informal construction, earthen materials are common in one story residential buildings in form of a mixture of locally available earth and fibers. They provide the level of affordability in informal and rural context that is acceptable by the local housing market. Developers of the informal urban housing in the

Kenyan construction industry tend to focus on the material affordability as the main priority. The quality and structural soundness is often a secondary consideration driven by desire to maximize profit. The occupants of the settlements have limited options due to their low economic capacity. The developers in these slum-like areas such as Mathare also focus on the construction delivery time and the general outlook of the final product from their potential client's perspective (Giulia Celentano & Habert, 2021). The use of this materials in urban centers has rapidly declined due to congestion that limits material availability within these localities. The material has been rapidly overtaken by use of iron sheets and prefabricated earthen bricks or adobe which consists of compressed earthen bricks that have been structurally stabilized with cement (Giulia Celentano & Habert, 2021). Despite the gain of traction of the earthen blocks and bricks in informal settlements, majority of the projects that use the earthen materials are initiated by non-profit organizations. This shows that informal developers have morphed their construction to the locally available and affordable mainstream concrete and stone blocks. The bricks are perceived to be expensive and their production outside the informal settlement neighborhood. still limits their acceptability. In most flood prone areas, the common material for walling construction is the soil-cement blocks produced from manual pressing machines. This is an advancement towards the engineered earthen masonry which include additional binders and enhancers to improve their structural, compressive and hygrothermal performances (Bruno et al., 2017; Obonyo, 2011). These blocks are not only sustainable

The formal real estate sector is highly driven by the push towards meeting the regulatory requirements. Standards and building codes inform major decisions when it comes to the choice of materials. Uptake of alternative building materials has been derailed by the lack of sufficient regulations that support the move towards these materials. An interview with construction industry professionals, Gieseckam et. al (2015) identified a concern relating to reliance of overdue regulations that promote the use of sustainable low carbon alternative materials in construction. The sector is dominated by convectional materials.

The Real estate developers also place great emphasis on the preferences of the end users of their developments. A high proportion of end users view the use of earthen masonry and alternative low carbon materials as unaesthetic and incapable of generating structurally sound buildings. Access to information concerning the structural performance of these materials is limited. Existing information has not been extensively incorporated into the building codes and standards to guide their scaled use in formal construction (Gieseckam et al., 2014, 2016). These shortcomings force the developers to continue with the use of the mainstream unsustainable masonry materials.

Enhancing adoption drivers for engineered earthen masonry in the form construction context

A scaled use of engineered earthen masonry can provide a pathway to meet the requirements for an increased supply of affordable housing as envisioned by the big four agenda of affordable housing (Diarte et al., 2020; Housing, 2018; Van Noppen, 2012). Technical engineering properties, cost and low embodied carbon and local availability set a baseline a shift from the non-conventional masonry (Cuéllar-Azcárate, 2016) .

Diverse strategies can be used to improve the uptake of earthen masonry systems by real estate developers. These strategies have been identified in literature as adoption drivers for scaled use of alternative low carbon building materials. However, there is lack of an ecosystem-based approach to support or improve on existing efforts within the industry. This is mainly due to the siloed working practices in construction (Cuéllar-Azcárate, 2016). Large scale developers have the capacity to influence small independent residential home builders to implement sustainable material within their project (Gieseckam et al., 2016). The resulting outcome of this approach is an industry-wide shift towards sustainable low-carbon built environment. Existing research outlines several strategies that can be used to scale the adoption of low carbon earthen construction materials. These strategies include the need for guiding regulations in the use engineered earthen materials. Standards and building codes pertaining to the structural, mechanical, and thermal performance of engineered masonry systems should be properly documented and continuously

improved to increase developers' confidence in the material. This must be accompanied by an increased awareness on the actual performance of the material through live case demonstrations and documenting on lessons learned from failures or weaknesses. A change management within organizations is also essential in guiding the shift from conventional to the alternative material such as the engineered earthen masonry (Gieseckam et al., 2016).

Construction clients are a major influence on the choice of a material to be used in construction in conjunction with the environmental conditions surrounding a development building project (Eze et al., 2021). Real estate developers form a large part of the construction industry clients as an inclusive supply chain can promote the confidence the developers have in a material. The producers of engineered earthen masonry must create marketing strategies that highlight on the production and improvements to the material to the developers to build their confidence in the use of material. This strategy can also help overcome the perception barriers among the developers

Creating awareness among the real estate developers on the engineering earthen masonry as a novel alternative to the conventional unsustainable and costly materials can be used as a strategy to scale the uptake of the material by developers. Perceived misconceptions due to lack of knowledge can be eliminated through awareness creation, training on the applicability of the material and developing live case studies with the earthen material to enhance uptake (Ghazvinian & Leung, 2021; Zami, 2021).

KEY FINDINGS FROM THE SUBJECT MATTER EXPERTS

The preliminary findings highlight the value that real estate developers place in meeting the requirements of their end-users when choosing the construction materials. Client and end user requirements are a major determining factor in the material selection process (Gieseckam et al., 2016). The real estate developers emphasize on the availability of materials as a major determinant in selection of the material. Improving on the supply chain to enhance availability of the engineered masonry can be a strategy to scale their uptake by the developers. A steady supply can generate economies of scale therefore stabilizing the cost of the earthen masonry to tackle the cost competitiveness in comparison to the mainstream stone and concrete masonry systems. Skilled construction workers are accustomed to the mainstream blocks. This limits the options that the developers have when choosing a walling material. The surveyed developers stressed that construction workers' knowledge in installing the material in large scale construction is a determinant since it impacts on productivity and delivery time of projects

Key Barriers from the Kenyan real estate perspective

The identified barriers to the uptake of engineered earthen masonry are in line with the literature on hinderances to adopting alternative low carbon materials.

Technical and cost data paucity

Sufficient formal documentation concerning the structural performances of engineered earthen masonry has not been made accessible to the real estate developers.

Insufficient documentation of tested concerns improvement scenarios

Concerns on lack of understanding on potential structural failures and responses of the engineered earthen masonry was also raised. This unawareness creates a skepticism to the use of the material.

Unstructured and disintegrated supply chain

A supply chain issue was also raised by the developers. There are insufficient suppliers to deliver the large volumes that might be required to meet the formal real estate construction demands. There is also limited knowledge on the existing suppliers of the engineered earthen masonry systems. The marketing strategies

used by suppliers does not also create sufficient impact to enhance penetration of the masonry system into the formal real estate developers' market.

Critical success factors for developing a unique value proposition that would result in developers embracing earthen masonry as a mainstream building material.

The process of mainstreaming the use of engineered earthen masonry is highly dependent on the market for this product. As earlier discussed, real estate developers influence a large share of the construction materials market. They can influence the use of the alternative materials into their projects thus scaling their uptake.

Training and capacity building on the use of the material

To achieve this goal real estate developers proposed the implementation of training and capacity building among the contractors and skilled construction workers on the use of the engineered earthen masonry.

Regulations and performance standards to guide adoption of earthen masonry

Availability of information concerning the technical field performance of the materials is lacking. The data can be provided through standards and regulations that support the use of the material as a move towards the low carbon sustainable construction in Kenya. A complete guide and documentation of the material properties, guides, technical data, advantages, limitations, cost, sources and logistics can be provided to developers to inform their choices during material selection in the design of their projects. This increases the confidence and knowledge concerning the earthen masonry therefore improving chances of adoption in large scale formal real estate projects.

Creating awareness among the developers and end users

Creating awareness among end users of the facilities is also an important aspect of scaling the uptake of the material. According to the surveyed real estate developers, the end users of their development projects have a high influence on the choice of construction materials. Making them knowledgeable on the benefits and the structural quality of the material can shift their perception towards the material and improve its market acceptability as observed by (Giulia Celentano & Habert, 2021). Some of the developers also lack sufficient knowledge on this material. This makes them not include the material as part of their selection of construction materials.

Cost data availability

Cost is a major consideration for materials to be used as they materials contribute to approximately 60% of the total construction cost, of which close to 14% of this amount goes to walling in conventional construction in Kenya (Gardner et al., 2019). Sufficient information on the cost of earthen masonry and suppliers can be a lever for scaling the use of this material by real estate developers. The limit to the use of the material is often presented by the scanty information to develop a cost benefit analysis and return on investment or lifecycle costs of the project.

Supply chain

Enhancing the supply chain to ensure availability of earthen masonry can help scale their application by real estate developers. The developers expressed concern on the lack of confidence of the supply sufficiency to meet their demand. The producers should work with the developers to scale the availability of the materials at the right time to meet the demand

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper sought to identify the roles that real estate developers can play in scaling the uptake of engineered masonry systems. Findings from literature and the survey indicate that real estate developers can upscale the use of the engineered earthen masonry if i) sufficient performance data, standards and building codes are available ii) awareness and training is provided to contractors and skilled workers on site on the use of

this low carbon material iii) Stabilized supply chain of the materials is developed by the producers to enhance constant availability iv) Cost standardization and competitiveness with the cheaper conventional blocks is established v) continuous improvement of the material performance and aesthetics by producers and industry practitioners vi) creating awareness among end users on the benefits of adopting this low carbon solution. As part of future work, we will be conducting focus group and interviews with the real estate development experts to get in depth information concerning the role they can play in scaling the uptake of this material.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest associated with the work presented herein

Data Availability

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request

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